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- **Fa-Lei WANG 2025: A new species of genus *Lepidiota* Kirby, 1828 from China (Coleoptera: Scarabaeidae: Melolonthidae). *The Indochina Entomologist*, 1 (54): 521–526.**

The following errors require correction:

1. On page 521, English Title and English Citation: “Melolonthidae” should be changed to “Melolonthinae”;
2. On page 521, Chinese Title and Chinese Citation: “鳃金龟科” should be changed to “鳃金龟亚科”;
3. On page 521, Chinese Citation: “霉鳃金龟” should be changed to “鳞鳃金龟”;
4. On page 525, Differential diagnosis, Line 9: “, see Prokofiev 2015.” should be changed to “, see Prokofiev 2015).”;
5. On page 525, Acknowledgements, Line 2: “who provided specimens of” should be changed to “who provided specimen of”.

